

Brian Paul Kaess & Ellen Byrd Elliott take a Family Vacation by Brian Paul Kaess

In December 1986, Brian Paul Kaess & Ellen Byrd Elliott were married and living in the Family Housing area (formerly Officer's quarters during WWII) at Fort Belvoir, Virginia, with Ellen's two children, Steven Ray Ellsberry¹ and Heather Marie Ellsberry, both from a prior marriage. They decided to take a family vacation during Christmas time to see her parents at their home in Xenia, Ohio, and also to visit Brian's brother Garret Thomas Kaess and his grandmother Margaret Jane (Swartz) Langley at his grandmother's home in the Edgewater neighborhood of Chicago. Brian managed to persuade his supervisor SSG Wooden to approve the leave.

So, one December day in 1986, they signed out 'on leave' with the kids at Fort Belvoir, packed up their new Renault Alliance front-wheel drive sedan, and cruised onto route 1 and headed north on vacation. U.S. military bases practically empty out during Christmas time and Fort Belvoir was no different. Passing through Washington, D.C., and heading into Maryland, the ride began uneventfully as their car raced past the rich farmlands while they drove along the highway. As they entered Pennsylvania, however, things began to change. They cruised in the morning mist at a higher altitude along the hazardous Pennsylvania turnpike that hugged the winding mountain roads, with treacherous overlooks of the lush valleys below, all the while racing past 18-wheeler trucks who steamed by in both directions. Not for the feint of heart!

They finally cruised by Wheeling, West Virginia, and emerged onto the flatter plains of the Ohio Valley, now the interstate highways becoming straighter and more predictable. They happily arrived to the small town of Xenia, Ohio, and Ellen's parents' home on Wyoming Drive. We were greeted by her dad Denver Ray Elliott, her mom Clay Willoughby Elliott, and her younger brother Alex Elliott, all living together. Both her parents spoke with a bit of a southern accent because they had been raised in Kentucky and Denver even looked like a 'throwback' to Elvis with his sideburns. He worked as a Defense Contractor at a local plant and I would later learn he was a member of the fraternal Mason's. He and Clay were both members of a Baptist church.

Ellen's teenage photo from high school graced their living room, showing how beloved their daughter was. She had high hopes of college success when she had earned a Band scholarship to Ohio State University her Senior Year, only to see those dreams doused in flames when she unexpectedly got pregnant with her 1st child during high school. She had been kicked out of NHS (National Honor Society) for 'immoral behavior' during this time frame, but hired a lawyer to fight back. In the end, she enlisted in the Army to help support her son Steven, and that was the path that took her up the ladder.

¹ SSG Steven Ray Ellsberry, Brian's former step-son, served in the U.S. Army in Iraq and Afghanistan, and earned a Purple Heart during his service. He suffered some sort of disability. Ellen stated she also did rotations as a U.S. Army Reserve Nurse in Iraq.

At this time, I was not only supporting Ellen, by sharing rent and expenses, but also sending \$50 a month back to my brother Garret in his bid to go to College too. I was also attending Community College courses on base as well, with the help of the Army Education Center at Belvoir. Now and then I would help Garret & grandma out with expenses, such as late taxes for the house, tuition, etc.; This may have cause tension in my marriage when Ellen said, 'What does he do for you!?'

Ellen mentioned how they had survived the 1974 Xenia tornado that destroyed part of Xenia and the surrounding area. She was also a bit afraid of her ex-husband Douglas 'Dougie' Ray Ellsberry, who lived in the area, and now and then, we would check the curtain blinds to see if he was outside watching us. A bit of a Ninja hobbyist, he was that kind of weirdo! He had spent time in prison for not paying child support and Ellen didn't seem to care if he stayed there. Ellen had showed me pictures of herself, when she was with Dougie, 'high' on drugs and alcohol. It seemed like she cleaned up a bit after she met me. I must have seemed 'plain' to her. She even had small tattoos on a couple of her fingers and one on her rear. She enjoyed listening to recordings of 'Hotel California' by *the Eagles*. She even liked dressing up her kids as punk rockers during Halloween.

While in Ohio, we took a short trip to rural Kentucky to meet the rest of Ellen's family and cousins. They were all friendly and I remember paper-plate food at picnics with jam to boot. This is when Ellen started calling me by a nickname 'Honey-Schnookums.' Ellen would later go to earn LPN and RN licenses as well as a Commission in the U.S. Army Reserve. She also worked at the VA in Dayton and as a Nursing Instructor. The last I heard she was on the Major's list for promotion.

Finally, we packed up again and headed for Chicago. We arrived at my grandma Margaret's house on Hollywood Ave. and met my grandma and twin-brother Garret. Ellen happily exclaimed 'Oh, that's nice, your grandma has a house.'

We stayed in the 1st floor bedroom and let the kids sleep upstairs in my former room. Ellen was restless and Chicago piqued her interest and so she urged me to 'show her the town,' but all I had in mind was to introduce her to my circle of friends from high school. We visited my friend Bob Gillis at his house on Balmoral and Ashland, and he and his family served us and the kids a nice, hot dinner. Winifred Gillis, Bob's dad, exclaimed, 'Boy, those are sure some well-behaved kids!' Win, an ex-Marine, would later come out to Ft. Belvoir and wait for a few days in the 15th Evac Hospital company parking lot in his RV just for a chance to see Brian, who was in the field at this time. The 1st Sgt. passed me a message and I managed to chat with Win from the window of my M1010 truck-ambulance for a few minutes when I pulled up beside him. Our joke in the Army back then was, 'Goin' to the field!'

Back to Chicago. Then, we visited the home of my ex-girlfriend Jennifer Mundt on Cullum Ave. in Ravenswood. Ellen was always razing me, 'he wants to go back to Chicago to see Jennifer!' Jennifer wasn't available (obviously) but we managed to see her mom Linda Mundt and things were cordial enough and went smoothly.

So, after about two-three weeks of vacationing, we headed back to Virginia and arrived safely to our rented home on Fort Belvoir, Virginia, after signing back in. It was back to Army life and the 'rat race.' I thought to myself, if I ever got out of the Army, the compass would point in all directions!

All in all, our trip to Ohio, Kentucky, and Illinois was truly memorable. I really enjoyed getting to know Ellen's family better, and it meant a lot to have her meet mine. It was a wonderful family getaway.